

Studies on the Interaction Between Iodine and the NN'-Dioxides of Some Twin-Site Donors*

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The $-C=N-N=C-$ group is well known to be a potential donor in metal complexes with the stability order depending on the benzenoid rings attached to it. For example the stability order is 1, 10-phenanthroline > 2, 2'-bipyridine > pyrazine.

The interaction of these compounds with electron acceptor iodine, is found to be similar. This article presents the studies of the NN'-dioxides of these donors with iodine. Equilibrium constants and IR data on these systems have been presented.

It has been shown that the bonding strength of the donors possessing the $-C=N-N=C-$ is of the order 1,10-phenanthroline > 2,2'-bipyridine > pyrazine in their interaction with the acceptor iodine in non-polar solvent carbontetrachloride¹. The study of the interaction between the NN'-dioxides of these twin-site donors with iodine has not so far been studied. As these NN'-dioxides are very slightly soluble in nonpolar solvents, it is proposed to study the interaction between the NN'-dioxides and iodine in aqueous medium and the solids obtained as result of the reaction between NN'-dioxides and iodine by IR spectroscopy.

Experimental

2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide^{2,3}, 1,10-phenanthroline-NN' dioxide⁴, and pyrazine NN'-dioxide^{5,6} were prepared by the methods already reported. The authenticity of the samples was established from its melting point, elemental analysis and IR data. The products were found to be chromatographically homogeneous.

All the UV-visible spectra were recorded on Unicam SP-700 recording spectrophotometer provided with temperature control equipment ($\pm 0.5^\circ$). 1.0 cm matched quartz cells were used for making spectral measurements. IR spectra were recorded on Carl Zeiss (Jena) UR-10, IR spectrophotometer.

Stock solutions of iodine⁷ and the NN'-dioxides were prepared by weighing and dissolution in water. Equilibrium constants for these systems have been determined following the method of Slifkin⁸.

Results and Discussion

From Fig. 1 it can be seen that the spectrum of iodine in water exhibits the absorption of the triiodide

ion and solvated iodine molecule. Katzin⁹ has reported that the triiodide formation may be due to the following reaction.

Iodine in nonpolar solvents has a peak at 520 nm¹⁰. The peak at 455 nm is the blue shifted iodine band in water, when the donor concentration is increased, it can be seen from Fig. 1, that there is an increase in the I_3^- absorbance (365) with a simultaneous decrease

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectrum of Pyrazine NN'-dioxide-iodine in aqueous medium.

X-axis—Wavelength in nm.

Y-axis—Absorbance

1. Iodine in water
2. $2.58 \times 10^{-3} M$ pyrazine NN'-dioxide (PYND) in (I)
3. $5.16 \times 10^{-3} M$ PYND in (I)
4. $7.74 \times 10^{-3} M$ PYND in (I)
5. $10.3 \times 10^{-3} M$ PYND in (I)
6. $12.9 \times 10^{-3} M$ PYND in (I)

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Fig. 2. Plot of Optical Density at 365 nm versus concentration of base

X-axis—concentration—M
 Y-axis—Optical Density
 (A) 1,10-Phenanthroline NN'-Dioxide
 (B) 2,2'-Bipyridine NN'-Dioxide
 (C) Pyrazine NN'-Dioxide

of the 455 nm band. The plot of the log (A) (A=absorbance) against log (D) (D=concentration) is linear with a slope equal to unity (Fig. 2). This suggests that the complex formed is 1 : 1 which derives support from the following points.

1. Linearity in the I_3^- absorbance values with donor concentration.
2. Isosbestic point at 405 μm (Fig. 1.)

The equilibrium constant values are calculated employing the following equation ^{8,11},

$$K = \frac{C_1(D_0 - D_2) + C_2(D_1 - D_0)}{C_1 C_2 (D_2 - D_1)} \quad \dots [3]$$

where D_0, D_1, D_2 are the optical densities measured at a fixed wavelength with constant iodine concentration and C_1 and C_2 are varying concentrations of donor respectively. The data are presented in Table 1. The wide scatter in K values may be due to hydrogen bonding of these donors in aqueous medium.

From the above considerations the interaction between the donors and iodine can be represented

TABLE I(A)—CALCULATION OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS

S. No.	System	No. assigned in the mixture.	Concentration of the base ($10^{-3}M$)	Absorbance at 365 nm (D)
1.	Pyrazine NN'-dioxide + Iodine	0	0.00	0.12
		1	2.58	0.18
		2	5.16	0.23
		3	7.74	0.29
		4	10.32	0.38
2.	2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide + Iodine	5	12.91	0.45
		0	0.00	0.12
		1	2.58	0.20
		2	5.16	0.27
		3	7.74	0.36
3.	1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide + Iodine.	4	10.33	0.42
		5	12.91	0.49
		0	0.00	0.12
		1	0.40	0.20
		2	0.80	0.27
		3	1.21	0.34
		4	1.61	0.44
		5	2.62	0.54

TABLE I(B)—CALCULATION OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS

S. No.	System	Mixtures	Equilibrium constant K (litres/mole)
1.	Pyrazine NN'-dioxide + Iodine	012	29.70
		013	41.09
		014	24.22
		015	18.08
		023	72.10
		024	28.50
		025	20.95
		034	52.38
		035	29.70
		045	72.52
			Average
2.	2,2'-bipyridine-NN'-dioxide + Iodine	012	85.72
		013	38.71
		014	27.27
		015	20.55
		023	55.59
		024	53.70
		025	36.30
		034	80.13
		035	45.86
		045	82.40
			Average
3	1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide + Iodine	012	547.54
		013	258.28
		014	164.88
		015	119.27
		023	468.84
		024	225.50
		025	145.62
		034	430.56
		035	209.11
		045	405.61
			Average

by^{1,2}.

The above scheme is analogous to the interaction of iodine with the original base in nonpolar solvents¹.

The interaction^{7,8} of the aromatic amines, aminoacids, proteins and β -carotene with iodine in nonpolar solvents is reported to take place through the formation of outer complex with the subsequent transformation of this to inner complex.

Further, the solids obtained by the interaction of these NN'-dioxides with iodine in aqueous solution and slow evaporation of the solvent under low pressure showed the presence of iodine as evidenced by the characteristic 360 nm band. This supports the idea that iodine in the final product is in the ionic form⁸. That the solids obtained contain iodine in the ionic

form is further confirmed by the well known starch-iodine reaction.

The methanolic solutions of the donors with iodine also gave the characteristic 360 nm band (iodine $1.9 \times 10^{-3} M$ + saturated solutions of the donors) indicating the ionic form of iodine to be present in this medium. However, in chloroform the shifted iodine bands are observed (with saturated solutions of the donors + iodine $8.92 \times 10^{-4} M$ keeping same concentration of iodine as reference).

1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide ——— 485 nm

2,2 -bipyridine NN'-dioxide ——— 500 nm

Pyrazine NN'-dioxide ——— 505 nm

IR Spectra of the solids :

All the solids between these NN'-dioxides and iodine are prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of

the donor and iodine, and the water removed slowly' at reduced pressure. The IR spectra were taken in nujol mull.

From the IR spectral data (Table 2) of the above solid complexes it can be seen that the $\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$ of the NN'-dioxides shift to lower frequency on complex formation. Further the stretching frequency difference $\Delta\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$ is in the following order. 1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide > 2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide \approx pyrazine NN'-dioxide.

this fact is supported by the presence of two very strong $>N \rightarrow O$ stretching absorption at 1262 cm^{-1} and 1255 cm^{-1} in its IR spectrum. However, on complexation the 1265 cm^{-1} and 1255 cm^{-1} bands are found to shift to 1235 cm^{-1} and 1228 cm^{-1} respectively. The similar trend in the shift of $>N \rightarrow O$ bending vibrations is also observed. In the case of pyrazine NN'-dioxide the bands appearing at 1270^{-1} and 880 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to $>N \rightarrow O$ stretching vibration and bending vibration respectively shift to lower frequencies (1240 cm^{-1} and 845 cm^{-1}) on complex formation. In the case of 1, 10=

TABLE 2 -OBSERVED N - O FREQUENCIES OF SOME NN'-DIOXIDES AND THEIR IODINE COMPLEXES

S. No.	Compounds	N-O stretch (cm^{-1})	N-O bend (cm^{-1})
1.	Pyrazine NN'-dioxide	1270	889
2.	Pyrazine NN'-dioxide+Iodine	1240	845
3.	2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide	1265 1255	855 840
4.	2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide + Iodine	1235 1228	835 815
5.	1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide	1255 1210 (Sh)	864 856 (Sh)
6.	1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide+Iodine	1215 1200 (Sh)	848 832 (Sh)

Sh=Shoulder

The active site of the $>N \rightarrow O$ bond for complex formation with iodine is presumably the oxygen atom, as the stretching frequency of $>N \rightarrow O$ bond shifts to lower frequency in all the cases. The shift of $\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$ to lower frequency seems to be ascribable to charge transfer from an oxygen n-type orbital to the iodine σ_u^* -antibonding orbital, which decreases the electron density at the oxygen atom so that the π -electron resonance interaction of the oxygen 2p π -electrons with the rest of the π -system is weakened.

Kubota *et al*¹³ and Kulevesky and Severson¹⁴ reported similar changes in the stretching frequency of $>N \rightarrow O$ bond on complexation with iodine in the case of aromatic N-oxides in organic solvents.

Simpson and his co-workers^{2,15} observed changes in the $>N \rightarrow O$ stretching band to lower frequencies upon complex formation with transition metal. It was argued that the uncoordinated 2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide molecule in the solid state most likely exists in the staggered conformation unlike 2,2'-bipyridine and

phenanthroline NN'-dioxide, two bands appear in the original base at 1255 cm^{-1} (broad) and 1210 cm^{-1} (weak). The two bands are probably due to repulsions of the two $>N \rightarrow O$ groups leading to somewhat distorted configuration. On complexation with iodine the stretching and bending vibrations are shifted to lower frequencies i.e., at 1215 cm^{-1} and 1200 cm^{-1} .

As can be seen from Table 2, the order of the shift of frequency is pyrazine NN'-dioxide \approx 2,2'-bipyridine NN'-dioxide < 1,10-phenanthroline NN'-dioxide, similar to that when equilibrium constants in aqueous medium are considered.

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